

OPTIMUM DESIGN OF INTERFACIAL BONDING OF FIBER REINFORCED CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Based on the fracture mechanism of ceramic matrix composites (CMC), a 3-D micromechanical model is presented in this paper. The fracture mode of the interface is a mixed mode of Mode I and Mode II. The driving forces for the interfacial damage are the rates of strain energy released. The stresses near the interface due to residual thermal stress are analyzed by 3-D Finite Element Method with 20 nodes. The critical strain-energy density factors with different interfacial debonding lengths are calculated. From the relations between critical strain-energy densities and interfacial debonding lengths, the optimum debonding length which makes the critical strain-energy density factor minimum is found.

KEYWORDS: Ceramic Matrix Composites; Interfacial Debonding; Residual Thermal Stress; Fracture Toughness; Mixed Mode; Strain-Energy Density Factor.

I. INTRODUCTION

In fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites, the nature of the interface will play a significant role in the type of fracture. If the interfacial bond is too strong, cracks will propagate into the fiber from the matrix and an undesirable brittle fracture occurs. Whereas if the interfacial bond is too weak, then the insufficient energy will be absorbed in fracture and delamination and buckling may arise. Hence, the interface should be moderately bonded. That is, the need to produce CMC with interface optimized to meet specific material requirements, for instance, fracture toughness. Therefore, how to design and control the interface are very important problems.

Due to misfit of the elastic coefficients of fiber and matrix, the interface of CMC is subjected to thermal residual stress, which can be on the order of giga-pascal and matrix debonds and allows the main crack to propagate beyond the fiber which remains intact. The intact fiber then bridges the crack faces, exerting a closing traction which shields the crack tip from the stress applied to the materials.

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fracture mode of the interface is a mixed mode of Mode I and Mode II. The driving forces for the interfacial damage are the rates of strain energy released. The stresses near the interface due to residual thermal stress are analyzed by 3D Finite Element method with 20 nodes.

The critical strain-energy density factors with different interfacial debonding lengths are calculated, then the optimum debonding length which makes the critical strain-energy density factor minimum is found. This optimum interfacial debonding length is very useful for control and design of interface of CMC.

II. FRACTURE MECHANISM AND MICROMECHANICAL MODEL

As mentioned above, the residual stress can cause that the interface between fiber and matrix debonds and allows the main crack to propagate beyond the fiber which remains intact as shown in Figure 1. The intact fiber then bridges the crack faces, exerting a closing traction which shields the crack tip from the stress applied to the material.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of crack propagation through a reinforced ceramic matrix composite

Based on the fracture mechanism as shown in Figure 1, a 3D micromechanical model is presented in Figure 2.

Due to symmetry, only one half section divided into 108 elements is considered. The method of isoparametric elements with twenty nodes is employed.

III. FRACTURE ANALYSIS

Using mechanics of materials approach, which is assumed that the strains in the fiber direction of a unidirectional fibrous composite are the same in the fibers as in the matrix, the residual thermal stresses in the fiber and matrix are

Figure 2. 3D Micromechanical model of CMC

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{fL} &= E_f E_m V_m \frac{\alpha_m - \alpha_f}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m} \Delta T \\ \sigma_{mL} &= E_f E_m V_f \frac{\alpha_f - \alpha_m}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m} \Delta T \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where E_f, E_m are Yong's modulus of fiber and matrix; V_f, V_m are volume fractions of fiber and matrix; α_f, α_m are coefficients of thermal expansions of fiber and matrix, and ΔT is temperature gradient.

Notice $\Delta T < 0$, when $\alpha_m > \alpha_f$, the fiber is under residual compression, and the matrix is under tension, The fracture mode of the interface is a mixed mode of Mode I and Mode II. The stresses and strains due to residual thermal stress with different interfacial debonding lengths for Mode I and Mode II will be analyzed by 3D Finite Element method. Then the strain energy U for Mode I and Mode II are

$$\begin{aligned} U_1 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum \sigma_i \varepsilon_i \\ U_2 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum \sigma_r \varepsilon_i \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

For Mode I, U_1 is decreasing as the interfacial surface A_1 is increasing, therefore, the rate of strain energy released is

$$G_I = - \frac{\partial U}{\partial A} \quad (3)$$

For Mode II, U_2 is increasing as A_2 is increasing, therefore

$$G_{II} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial A} \quad (4)$$

By theory of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics, the stress intensity factor for Mode I and Mode II are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} K_I &= \sqrt{E_1 G_1} \\ K_{II} &= \sqrt{E_2 G_2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E_1 &= E_f V_f + E_m V_m \\ E_2 &= \frac{E_f E_m}{E_f V_m + E_m V_f} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

The strain energy factor $S^{[5]}$ is expressed as

$$S = a_{11} K_I^2 + 2a_{12} K_I K_{II} + a_{22} K_{II}^2 \quad (7)$$

Obviously, S is a function of K_I and K_{II} , where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a_{11} &= \frac{1}{16G} [(3 - 4\gamma - \cos\theta)(1 + \cos\theta)] \\ a_{12} &= \frac{1}{16G} (2\sin\theta) [\cos\theta - (1 - 2\gamma)] \\ a_{22} &= \frac{1}{16G} [4(1 - \gamma)(1 - \cos\theta) + (1 + \cos\theta)(3\cos\theta - 1)] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8)$$

Here, θ is the angle of crack,

$$G = \frac{G_m G_f}{V_m G_f + V_f G_m} \quad (9)$$

$$\gamma = V_f \gamma_f + V_m \gamma_m \quad (10)$$

where G_m, G_f are shear modulus of matrix and fiber, γ_m, γ_f are Poisson's ratios of matrix and fiber.

The criterion for the crack which will propagate is

$$\text{When } \theta = \theta_c, \quad \frac{\partial S}{\partial \theta} = 0, \quad S = S|_{\theta=\theta_c} = S_c \quad (11)$$

By substituting $\theta = \theta_c$ in Equation (7), S_c , critical strain energy density factor, will be obtained. θ_c is called critical angle of fracture.

Obviously, the critical strain energy density factors vary with the interfacial debonding lengths. From this relation, the optimum debonding length which makes the critical strain energy density factor minimum will be found.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Silicon carbide fiber reinforced zirconium oxide composites (SiC/ZrO₂) are considered. The properties are:

$$E_m = 200 \text{ GPa}, \quad E_f = 350 \text{ GPa}, \quad V_m = 78.2\%, \quad V_f = 21.8\%$$

$$\gamma_m = 0.2, \quad \gamma_f = 0.21;$$

$$\Delta T = -1000^\circ\text{C}, \quad \alpha_m = 10 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}, \quad \alpha_f = 5 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}.$$

The interfacial debonding lengths are decreasing toward the tip of matrix cracking as shown in Figure 2. Hence, six conditions of interfacial debonding lengths are considered. They are 10 : 10 : 5 (μm); 12 : 12 : 6 (μm); 14 : 14 : 7 (μm); 16 : 16 : 8 (μm); 18 : 18 : 9 (μm); and 20 : 20 : 10 (μm). The computation of stress intensity factor of Mode I for different interfacial debonding length is summarized in Table 1. Obviously, the strain energy U decreases as the debonding surface A increases. therefore,

$G_I = -\frac{\partial U}{\partial A}$. The computation of stress intensity factor of Mode II for different interfacial debonding length is summarized in Table 2.

Table 1. Stress Intensity Factor of Mode I

Debonding Length (μm)	Debonding Surface Area $A (10^{-10}\text{m}^2)$	Strain Energy U ($10^{-7}\text{N} \cdot \text{m}$)	Rate of strain Energy Released $G_I = -\frac{\partial U}{\partial A} (\text{N} \cdot \text{m}/\text{m}^2)$	Stress Intensity Factor $K_I (\text{GN}/\text{m}^{3/2})$
10 : 10 : 5	40. 007963	0. 412840	17. 936933	64. 605915
12 : 12 : 6	43. 149556	0. 336286	13. 256492	55. 540847
14 : 14 : 7	46. 291486	0. 299566	10. 007589	48. 257289
16 : 16 : 8	49. 432741	0. 278914	7. 696179	42. 319037
18 : 18 : 9	52. 574334	0. 266743	6. 015044	37. 412750
20 : 20 : 10	55. 715927	0. 259937	4. 768881	33. 312439

Table 2. Stress Intensity Factor of Mode II

Debonding Length (μm)	Debonding Surface Area $A (10^{-10}\text{m}^2)$	Strain Energy U ($10^{-7}\text{N} \cdot \text{m}$)	Rate of strain Energy Released $G_{II} = -\frac{\partial U}{\partial A} (\text{N} \cdot \text{m}/\text{m}^2)$	Stress Intensity Factor $K_{II} (\text{GN}/\text{m}^{3/2})$
10 : 10 : 5	15. 707963	0. 0657314	1. 694359	19. 333277
12 : 12 : 6	18. 849556	0. 0760914	2. 439877	23. 199932
14 : 14 : 7	21. 991486	0. 0865714	3. 321045	27. 067000
16 : 16 : 8	25. 132741	0. 098560	4. 337559	30. 933243
18 : 18 : 9	28. 274334	0. 112606	5. 489723	34. 799898
20 : 20 : 10	31. 415927	0. 129269	6. 777436	38. 666554

Table 3. Critical Strain Energy Density Factor

Debonding length (μm)	Critical Angle of Fracture θ_c (Degree)	Critical Strain Energy Density Factor S_{cr} (GN/m)
10 : 10 : 5	266. 3972	16. 85336
12 : 12 : 6	255. 1635	14. 78660
14 : 14 : 7	243. 9297	13. 94079
16 : 16 : 8	234. 1002	14. 18245
18 : 18 : 9	225. 6749	14. 91606
20 : 20 : 10	218. 6538	16. 38328

By use of Equation (7), strain energy density factor for each interfacial debonding length will be obtained. Then from Equation (11), the critical angle of fracture θ_c and critical strain energy density factor S_{cr} will be computed. These results are summarized in Table3. This critical strain energy density factor vs the interfacial debonding length l_{DL} can be drawn and adjusted by method of least squares as shown in Figure3.

This curve is a parabola which can be expressed as

$$S_{cr} = 0. 1071l_{DL}^2 - 3. 2374l_{DL} + 38. 3926 \quad (12)$$

Obviously, when $l_{DL} = 15.1148\mu\text{m}$, $(S_{cr})_{\min} = 13.9263\text{GN/m}$. Therefore, the optimum interfacial debonding length which makes the critical strain energy density factor minimum is $15.1148\mu\text{m}$.

Figure 3. Critical Strain Density Factor vs Interfacial Debonding Length

A high-resolution transmission electron micrograph of the interface between silicon carbide fiber and ZrO_2 matrix reveals a thin layer of silicate phase. This is third phase with thickness $5\sim 25\mu\text{m}$ which is not considered in the micromechanical model as shown in Figure 2.

V. CONCLUSION

1. Based on the fracture mechanism of CMC, a 3D micromechanical model is presented.
2. The fracture mode of the interfacial debonding is a mixed mode of Mode I and Mode II. The critical strain energy factor is employed to predicate the optimum interfacial debonding length of CMC
3. The residual thermal stress of the interface plays an important role in the predication of optimum interfacial debonding length of CMC. This residual stress should be checked by experiment results using Ramen Laser Spectrum Technique.
4. The third phase between fiber and matrix should be considered in the micromechanical model in the optimum design of interfacial bonding of CMC.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China.